
bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for
innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of marine and coastal geohazard

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New curriculum design on Marine Geo-Hazard assessment and Sustainability of Coastal Regions

BridgET Project Result 09

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BridgET: Bridging the gap between the land and the sea in a virtual environment for innovative teaching and community involvement in the science of climate change-induced marine and coastal geohazard

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PROJECT RESULT REPORT

09 - New Curriculum Design on Marine Geohazard Assessment and Sustainability of Coastal Regions

Executive Summary

This project result represents the culmination and integration of the experiences, outputs, and pedagogical innovations developed throughout the BridgEt project. Rather than producing a single technical output, Project Result 09 focuses on the transformation of these results into a coherent educational framework that can support curriculum renewal and teaching innovation across institutions involved in marine geosciences.

Over the course of the project, partners (teacher and students included) co-developed and co-created a rich body of materials including interactive platforms, 3D and VR-ready datasets, methodological guides, and immersive field-based learning experiences. These resources, were created and tested during three international summer schools and through collaboration with students, educators, and industry stakeholders, provided the foundation for designing a flexible and modular curriculum aligned with emerging educational needs and sustainability goals.

The work carried out under this result has led to the formulation of three complementary deliverables:

- A **Curriculum Design Document**, which outlines the pedagogical structure, core competencies, and modular options for a teaching pathway in marine geohazards and coastal sustainability.
- A **Sample Teaching Module (Syllabus)** focused on coastal hazard assessment using immersive and digital tools, already piloted and planned for formal integration into the academic year 2026/2027.
- An annotated **Inventory of VR/3D Educational Resources**, which consolidates and organises the digital materials developed within the project and ensures open access via platforms such as ZENODO, and the Erasmus+ Project Results Platform.

Rather than proposing a rigid program, this project result provides a scalable, adaptable model that can be integrated into existing Master's programs or inspire new interdisciplinary teaching initiatives. It places strong emphasis on experiential learning, data-driven analysis, and cross-sectoral skills, making it highly relevant to both academic and professional contexts.

This curriculum design is intended not only as a final product, but as a living framework that can grow and evolve with future projects, institutional strategies, and technological developments.

List of Deliverables:

Deliverable 9.1: Curriculum Design for Marine Geo-Hazard Assessment and Coastal Sustainability

Deliverable 9.2: Sample Teaching Module Syllabus – Coastal and Marine Geo-Hazards

Deliverable 9.3: Annotated Inventory of VR/3D Educational Resources all accessible via platforms such as ZENODO, the Erasmus+ Project Results Platform and project website (<https://bridget.unimib.it/>)

1. Project Result 09 – Deliverable overview

Below is a description of the deliverable produced as part of project result “New curriculum design on marine geohazard assessment and sustainability of coastal regions”.

Deliverable 9.1 – Curriculum Design for Marine Geo-Hazard Assessment and Coastal Sustainability

Description: A proposal for the generation of a modular curriculum framework integrating learning outcomes, teaching strategies, and proposed modules for marine geo-hazards and coastal sustainability education.

Type of Output: Curriculum Framework Document

Language: English

Access/Format: PDF Document

Access Level: Public

Attachment/link: Curriculum Design Document.pdf

Deliverable 9.2 – Sample Teaching Module Syllabus – Coastal and Marine Geo-Hazards

Description: A syllabus for a 6 ECTS teaching module using immersive content, real-world datasets, and interactive exploration tools, piloted during the project and planned for implementation.

Type of Output: Teaching Module / Syllabus

Language: English

Access/Format: PDF Document

Access Level: Public

Attachment/link: Sample Teaching Module.pdf

Deliverable 9.3 – Annotated Inventory of VR/3D Educational Resources

Description: A structured inventory of VR, 3D, and interactive resources created during the BridgET project, with links to platforms (ThingLink, Story Maps, etc.) and open access on ZENODO.

Type of Output: Annotated Resource Inventory

Language: English

Access/Format: PDF Document with Hyperlinks (Zenodo + Project Website)

Access Level: Public

Attachment/link: ZENODO “BridgET” community:

https://zenodo.org/communities/bridget_erasmus/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

Deliverable 9.1

Curriculum Design for Marine Geo-Hazard Assessment and Coastal Sustainability

1. Introduction and Rationale

The increasing exposure of coastal regions to geo-hazards and climate-related risks calls for new professional profiles equipped with multidisciplinary skills in marine sciences, digital geo-technologies, and sustainability planning. Within the framework of the Erasmus+ BridgET project, we defined a set of criteria that should be taken into consideration when designing a curriculum for higher education, to make it respond to key needs expressed by academic partners, students, and industry stakeholders. Our proposed curriculum was especially shaped through the analysis of and results obtained from what we experienced during the project, especially during the organization and implementation of summer schools.

In particular, we integrated the findings from:

- A comparative analysis of MSc programmes and course gaps across partner universities (PR01)
- Stakeholder consultations with industry representatives and NGOs regarding employability needs
- Practical experiences and feedback from three international summer schools (Santorini, Milan, Magoodhoo) and the student feedback (PR01)
- The outcomes and learning contents developed across Project Results 2–8

The most notable feedback we had (from students but also stakeholders) highlighted the importance of more digital and practical content, real case studies and field-oriented teaching and a broader international and interdisciplinary exposure.

We hereafter present some specific aspects and how they should be outlined when designing a flexible and modular learning path that promotes innovation, practical engagement, and knowledge transfer in support of the green and blue economy.

2. Learning Objectives and Outcomes

In the urgent context of the present-day challenges which include climate change and geo-risks, energy transition and sustainability, graduates should be able to:

- Assess geohazards in coastal and marine environments using advanced geospatial tools
- Apply digital technologies such as photogrammetry, bathymetry, and VR for environmental modelling (this latter applied to predict future scenarios, define mitigation strategies and restoration actions, and guide measures for energy transition)
- Design sustainable coastal management strategies informed by scientific data
- Communicate scientific results to diverse stakeholders, including policymakers and the public
- Collaborate in interdisciplinary and multicultural contexts

3. Curriculum Structure and Modules

The curriculum has been designed and proposed by the BridgET project partnership, to be integrated within existing MSc programs or developed as a stand-alone pathway. Considering “core modules” and “elective modules”, an ideal structure is proposed as follow:

Core Modules

Module Title	Description
<i>Marine Geohazards and Risk Assessment</i>	Scientific and methodological principles, case studies
<i>Coastal Systems and Climate Challenges</i>	Physical and socio-environmental dynamics
<i>Spatial Data Acquisition and 3D Modelling</i>	UAV, ROV, bathymetry, underwater photogrammetry
<i>Virtual and Immersive Learning in Marine Sciences</i>	VR/XR environments, digital communication
<i>Geoscience for Sustainability and Policy</i>	Green/blue economy, impact assessment

Elective Modules (Flexible Path):

Elective module could be designed to allow students to specialize in:

- Major *geo-hazard*, representing relevant issue for society (e.g.: Volcanic island systems), observed also from a human geography context
- *Geo-Biodiversity* loss (e.g. coral reef monitoring; deep-sea resources)
- *Polar/extreme* environments
- Environmental *geophysics* and resources
- Applied *remote sensing*

Practical Activities and Internship Opportunities

A strong focus should be placed on hands-on learning, this aspect was of primary importance during the three BridgET summer school and allowed engaging students more directly, making them facing real scenarios or data processing/interpretation, co-creating results and data analysis with teachers. Options include:

- Field-based summer schools (where scientific topics can be seen in a true context and connected with the socio-economic realm of the case study)
- VR-based laboratory activities (e.g., toolkit exploration, 3D model building)
- Use of professional software (e.g., Agisoft Metashape, ArcGIS, etc...)
- Internships or applied project work in collaboration with research centres or industry

These elements ensure the development of both technical skills and real-world problem-solving abilities.

5. Pedagogical Model and Flexibility

The proposed programme should be ideally built upon a **flexible and modular** pedagogical model that can be adapted to a wide range of institutional contexts and academic traditions. Rather than following a rigid structure, the curriculum allows for customisation and integration within existing Master's programs in marine sciences, geology, environmental engineering, and related fields. This adaptability ensures its relevance across diverse educational systems and geographical regions.

The learning approach is conceived as **blended and experience-driven**, combining traditional classroom teaching with field-based activities, digital content, and immersive technologies. Students will engage in virtual simulations, remote data analysis, and on-site applications through summer schools or project-based modules, making learning both dynamic and applied.

An essential feature of the curriculum is its emphasis on **transversal competencies**, such as collaborative teamwork, interdisciplinary problem-solving, sustainability communication, and ethical awareness. These skills are not treated as add-ons but are critical part of the learning experience, preparing students to engage with complex societal and environmental challenges in a responsible and forward-thinking manner.

The curriculum further promotes interdisciplinary learning paths, allowing students to tailor their focus according to their background and interests. Whether coming from marine sciences, geotechnical disciplines, or spatial data analysis, learners are encouraged to build bridges between fields and to develop a holistic view of geo-hazard assessment and coastal sustainability.

7. Conclusion and Next Steps

The proposed curriculum design offers a scalable and replicable model to modernise marine geoscience education in Europe. It reflects not only the needs identified through academic and stakeholder consultations but also the practical outcomes of the BridgEt project's experimental teaching initiatives. Looking ahead, the next phase of development will focus on making the proposed modules widely accessible by publishing them on shared educational platforms used within and beyond the consortium. This will facilitate their integration into existing degree programs and ensure a broader impact across European institutions. A similar initiative has already been started at UiT, in collaboration with other project partners and with funding obtained by CAU (Kiel university) for the development of an online module on "extreme environments" (https://apps.open.uit.no/learning/course/course-v1:UiT+EX101+2024_test/progress). Bachelor, MSc and PhD student can get enrolled in the course and have access to learning contents, that consist in videos, quiz, slides, exercises, references, and link to other online resources. At the same time, all material produced during the project are already implemented as resource material in different courses in all the partner universities, especially the online resource produced with project result 03, the different story maps designed during the summer schools and the number of 3D models and other available dataset. Not less important are the numerous software tutorials made available during the schools, presentations and bibliography.

Finally, not less important, the curriculum is designed to be adaptive and future-oriented. As new datasets, technologies, and teaching tools become available, especially in the fields of virtual and extended reality, geospatial analysis, and climate modelling, there is a clear pathway for updating and evolving the content. Continuous feedback from students and educators, as well as engagement with industry partners, will guide this process and ensure the curriculum remains relevant and forward-looking in a rapidly changing world.

Deliverable 9.2

Sample Teaching Module Syllabus – Coastal and Marine Geo-Hazards

Course Title:

Coastal Geohazards: Mapping, Modelling and Communication Strategies

Course Level: Master's level (MSc) – 6 ECTS

Language: English

Course Description: This module introduces students to the characterisation, mapping and management of geo-hazards in coastal environments through a combination of theoretical lectures, digital tools, and immersive exploration. It integrates interactive content developed in the Erasmus+ BridgEt project (www.bridget.unimib.it), including 360° virtual tours, real-world datasets, and VR-compatible resources for education and outreach.

The course focuses on applied geospatial techniques (UAV photogrammetry, multibeam bathymetry, underwater modelling) and highlights how marine and coastal geohazards, such as erosion, slope instability, volcanism, biodiversity loss, and earthquakes, can be understood, visualised, and communicated to stakeholders and the public.

Learning Outcomes: Upon successful completion of the course, students will be able to:

- Identify and classify main types of coastal and/or marine geohazards
- Process multisource dataset to provide geospatial data (UAV, bathymetry, satellite) for analyzing coastal dynamics and/or submarine processes at different spatio/temporal scales.
- Explore and evaluate geohazard scenarios in immersive environments
- Communicate geohazard risks using visual storytelling tools (e.g., Story Maps, VR)
- Develop small-scale projects using real datasets from case study sites

Teaching Materials and Resources:

- Virtual Guide to Coastal Mapping Technologies and Virtual cruise (Project Results 03 and 08):

<https://cabuff.ceos.uni-kiel.de/tours/bridget/web/index.htm>

<https://www.thinglink.com/scene/1871662911974277606>

- Story Maps from Project Result 06 and 07:

Etna region: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/4067a77d69fd4d5e8ea7af3f9bfbbdb9> (PR06)

Magoodhoo Island: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/873e525df3af4ecc8f7c6e1861b1139e> (PR07)

- Geospatial Datasets (DOI-registered):

UAV and bathymetric datasets from Santorini, Ciclopi islands, and Magoodhoo:

1-BridgET - Santorini Summer School: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15095564>

2-BridgET – Mt. Etna Summer School: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15059291>

3-BridgET – Maldives Summer School: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15097231>

- VR-ready 3D models, dataset and guidelines from BridgET Project Results 04, 05 and 06 available by access to ZENODO BridgET community at:

https://zenodo.org/communities/bridget_erasmus/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

Course Structure and Activities (example)

Week	Topic	Activities
1	Introduction to Coastal Geohazards	Lecture + case studies
2	Data Acquisition Techniques	Practical on UAV, bathymetry
3	3D Modelling and VR Integration	Workshop on Agisoft and VR viewers
4	Virtual Exploration	Guided exploration of PR03/06/07 resources
5	Communication of Risk	Story Map creation + peer review
6	Final Project	Group project using real dataset (report + presentation)

Assessment Methods:

- Participation and practicals: 30%
- Story Map project: 30%
- Final group project: 40%

Prerequisites: Basic knowledge of GIS or spatial data recommended.

Note on Implementation

This module has been partially implemented in selected courses at partner universities and tested during BridgEt project activities. It will be formally introduced at Milano-Bicocca University (MSc in Marine Sciences) into the teaching offer starting from the academic year 2026/2027.

Deliverable 9.3

Annotated Inventory of VR/3D Educational Resources

1. Introduction

This deliverable provides an annotated inventory of immersive and interactive digital resources produced as part of the Erasmus+ BridgET project. These resources include 360° virtual tours, 3D models, Story Maps, teaching toolkits, and real-world datasets suitable for educational use. They have been created to support the teaching of marine geohazard assessment and coastal sustainability across a range of digital learning environments, including virtual reality (VR), web platforms, and GIS-based storytelling tools.

All publicly available materials are hosted on open-access repositories, either on the official Erasmus+ Project Results Platform (or on the BridgEt project website - <https://bridget.unimib.it/>) and by assigning a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) stored on ZENODO, to main Datasets (in addition to project results), ensuring long-term accessibility and citation tracking. The only exception is one internal report produced by Orthodrone GmbH, which remains restricted, although included in Project Result 02.

ON ZENODO the “bridgET project community was also created (https://zenodo.org/communities/bridget_erasmus/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest).

2. Repository and Archiving

All open resources are archived on or accessible through the following links:

- ZENODO.org: Community:

https://zenodo.org/communities/bridget_erasmus/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

- BridgEt Project Website: <https://bridget.unimib.it/>

- Erasmus+ Project Results Platform

The internal technical report by Orthodrone GmbH is archived for partner use only and not publicly released due to commercial confidentiality.

3. Use and Access

The digital resources included in this inventory have been developed to support higher education in the fields of marine sciences, geohazard assessment, and geospatial analysis. Designed with adaptability in mind, these materials can be integrated into a variety of teaching formats — including traditional, blended, and fully online learning environments.

They are particularly well-suited for use in university-level modules that aim to develop practical and analytical skills through the use of immersive tools and real-world datasets. Thanks to their modular design and open-access nature, instructors can easily incorporate them into existing courses or adapt them for workshops, seminars, or summer schools.

Beyond academic use, these resources can serve as reference material for other Erasmus+ initiatives and capacity-building programs focused on environmental sciences, digital learning, and science communication. Each asset is accompanied by metadata and, where applicable, includes use-case suggestions and connections to practical learning activities such as VR walkthroughs or spatial data analysis.

By making these tools openly accessible and pedagogically rich, the BridgEt project promotes wider adoption of immersive and interactive learning strategies across disciplines and institutions.

4. Overview of Resources

Project Result	Resource Type	Description	Platform/Link
PR02	Guidelines + Example Dataset	Guidelines for UAV-based bathymetry with real-world dataset (DOI available)	https://bridget.unimib.it/wp-content/uploads/sites/159/2025/03/BridgET_Project-Result-2.2.pdf https://bridget.unimib.it/wp-content/uploads/sites/159/2025/03/BridgET_Project-Result-2.3.pdf https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111459 (UAV dataset)
PR03	Interactive 360° Virtual Tour	Virtual guide showing coastal mapping technologies from land to deep sea, with embedded interviews and a scenario from land to sea created with real datasets.	https://cabuff.ceos.uni-kiel.de/tours/bridget/web/index.htm
PR04	Guideline	Guideline for underwater photogrammetry (dataset are available from other PRs)	Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111598
PR05	Story Map + PDF Toolkit	VR exploration of Santorini's volcanic seafloor using 360° content and educational storytelling.	https://arcg.is/1DSeTeo
PR06	Technical Report + Story Map	Santorini geohazard VR model – immersive experience and modelling guide. Etna coastal area story map	Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111598 https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/4067a77d69fd4d5e8ea7af3f9bfbdb9
PR07	Story Map	Magoodhoo Island geohazard and sustainability visualisation using integrated 3D datasets.	https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/873e525df3af4ecc8f7c6e1861b1139e
PR08	ThingLink Virtual Cruise	Interactive experience aboard the RV Kronprins Haakon with immersive scenes and onboard walkthrough.	https://www.thinglink.com/cene/1871662911974277606
PR09	Teaching Materials	Curriculum design, module syllabus, and references to all VR/3D resources	Zenodo: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111598

Note: All datasets used during summer schools (UAV imagery, bathymetry, photogrammetry sets) are available on Zenodo, with a DOI per single school:

- Summer school Santorini: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15095564>
- Summer school Mt. Etna: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15059291>
- Summer school Maldives: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15097231>